

Integrated glucose–insulin profiling during prolonged oral glucose tolerance testing reveals hidden metabolic heterogeneity beyond conventional glucose classification

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Aims. To determine whether conventional glucose-based oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) classification adequately captures post-load metabolic heterogeneity, and whether integrated glucose–insulin profiling identifies hidden dysregulation beyond standard glycaemic categories.

Methods. We analysed a retrospective cohort of 273 individuals undergoing prolonged 3-hour OGTT with simultaneous glucose and insulin measurements at 0, 30, 60, 90, 120, 150 and 180 min. Post-load glucose response patterns were classified using a hybrid OGTT scheme (hOGTT) combining conventional fasting and 2-hour criteria with intermediate time-point thresholds, yielding four categories: normal, impaired fasting glucose (IFG), impaired glucose tolerance (IGT) and diabetes. Insulin secretion patterns were independently classified into five physiological phenotypes based on the Crofts/Kraft classification system. Six OGTT-derived summary features capturing glucose burden and insulin response dynamics were used to construct a standardised multivariate metabolic representation, enabling quadrant-based profile allocation and continuous quantification of deviation from the physiological reference using a Mahalanobis-based dysregulation score.

Results. Post-load glucose response patterns and insulin secretion phenotypes were related but not interchangeable. Among normoglycaemic subjects, only 54.6% displayed a physiological insulin-response pattern, while the remainder showed evidence of altered insulin dynamics despite normal glucose values. Reactive hypoglycaemia was observed in 54 of 226 subjects (23.9%), with 79.6% of first events occurring after 120 min. The multivariate dysregulation score increased progressively from normal glucose regulation to IFG, IGT and diabetes. Notably, 72 of 150 normoglycaemic subjects (48.0%) exceeded the upper physiological reference range, indicating occult post-load dysregulation despite normal glucose classification.

Conclusions. Conventional glucose thresholds capture only part of post-load metabolic heterogeneity. Prolonged OGTT with integrated glucose–insulin profiling provides clinically relevant information beyond standard glucose classification and may improve metabolic phenotyping.

Keywords: glucose tolerance test; insulin-response phenotypes; metabolic phenotyping; post-load dysmetabolism; reactive hypoglycaemia; type 2 diabetes.

Highlights

Glucose-response categories and insulin-response phenotypes were related but not interchangeable during prolonged oral glucose tolerance testing.

Nearly half of subjects with normal glucose curves lay outside the physiological 6D Q1 reference range.

Most first reactive hypoglycaemic events occurred after 120 min.

Integrated glucose–insulin profiling identified structured metabolic heterogeneity beyond conventional glucose classification.

A Q1-based Mahalanobis score provided a continuous measure of deviation from physiological OGTT dynamics.

1 Introduction

Type 2 diabetes arises from variable combinations of insulin resistance, beta cell dysfunction and altered post-load metabolic regulation. Despite this complexity, the oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) is still interpreted in routine practice mainly through fasting and 2 h glucose thresholds. This approach is clinically useful, but it reduces a dynamic physiological response to a limited number of static diagnostic points and may therefore underestimate biologically relevant heterogeneity (1).

Over the last two decades, increasing evidence has shown that the shape of the glucose curve during the OGTT contains information not captured by conventional glucose categories alone. Glucose curve morphology, peak timing and overall trajectory have been linked to differences in insulin sensitivity, beta cell function and future diabetes risk, even among individuals without overt diabetes. Latent-trajectory approaches have further reinforced the concept that OGTT responses are structured rather than random, and that

individuals with similar fasting or 2h glucose values may still belong to distinct metabolic phenotypes (2–4).

If this is true for glucose dynamics, it is likely to be even more relevant for insulin dynamics, because the insulin response represents the physiological counterpart of the glycaemic excursion. Kraft and Nosal highlighted decades ago that simultaneous insulin measurements during prolonged OGTTs could disclose abnormalities not apparent from glucose concentrations alone. More recent studies have supported this view, showing that delayed or sustained insulin-response patterns are associated with reduced insulin sensitivity, impaired early secretory responses and higher risk of future type 2 diabetes, independently of conventional glucose classification. Studies combining glucose and insulin curve morphology have likewise suggested that joint interpretation of both trajectories provides a deeper characterisation of metabolic phenotypes than glucose data alone (5–9).

Accordingly, the present study analysed a 3h OGTT dataset including simultaneous glucose and insulin measurements and parallel glucose-based and insulin-based classifications. We aimed to determine whether glucose-based categorisation alone is sufficient to describe metabolic heterogeneity, whether insulin-response phenotypes uncover clinically relevant substructure within and across glucose categories, and whether the relationship between glucose and insulin dynamics follows an organised metabolic architecture rather than random variation. To address these questions, we combined descriptive phenotype mapping with multivariate, geometric and distance-based analyses.

2 Methods

2.1 Study design and dataset contents

This was a retrospective observational study based on a cohort of 273 individuals who underwent a prolonged 3h oral glucose tolerance test. Plasma glucose and insulin were measured at 0, 30, 60, 90, 120, 150 and 180 min. Additional baseline variables included age, sex, BMI, height, weight and triglycerides. The dataset was designed to support integrated analysis of glycaemic dynamics, insulin-response patterns and derived metabolic indices from the OGTT. This study is reported in accordance with the STROBE guidelines for observational studies.

2.2 Phenotypic classification of glucose and insulin curves

All participants underwent a prolonged OGTT with plasma glucose and insulin measured at 0, 30, 60, 90, 120, 150 and 180 min. Glucose values were expressed in mg/dL and insulin values in mU/L. For index computation, glucose was converted to mmol/L (factor 0.0555) and insulin to pmol/L (factor 5.972).

Glucose curves were classified using a hybrid OGTT-based scheme (hOGTT) combining conventional fasting and 120 min criteria with predefined intermediate

thresholds at 30, 60 and 90 min. The 60 min threshold of 155 mg/dL was based on the 1-hour post-load plasma glucose criterion proposed for identification of high-risk individuals (1). The 30 min threshold of 175 mg/dL was derived from published ROC analyses of 30-minute plasma glucose for detection of prediabetes (1). Although the category labels mirror conventional ADA terminology, hOGTT classification incorporates additional intermediate time-point criteria and should not be treated as equivalent to standard ADA diagnostic categories (Figure 1). Insulin curves were classified according to a Crofts/Kraft-like pattern system into KC-I, KC-IIA, KC-IIB, KC-III and KC-V; KC-IV was predefined but not observed in the cohort (10, 11).

2.3 Conventional fasting and dynamic indices

Conventional fasting- and OGTT-derived indices were calculated according to their original published descriptions. Fasting-derived metrics included standard measures of insulin resistance and beta cell function, lipid-linked indices, and model-based parameters. Dynamic OGTT-derived metrics included established measures of insulin sensitivity and insulin secretion, including Matsuda-type, insulinogenic, disposition, Stumvoll, Kanauchi, Gutt, OGIS and related indices (12–18).

2.4 Reactive hypoglycaemia analysis

Reactive hypoglycaemia was analysed in the merged core dataset comprising subjects with complete OGTT information over the full 0–180 min interval and available glucose-response classification. Reactive hypoglycaemia was defined as the occurrence of at least one glucose value below 54 mg/dL at any OGTT time point. For each subject, we extracted the presence of reactive hypoglycaemia, time of first event, nadir glucose concentration, hypoglycaemic duration and cumulative glucose deficit below threshold. Hypoglycaemic onset was classified according to timing of the first event: before 120 min, at 120 min, or after 120 min. Late reactive hypoglycaemia was further characterised within the 120–150–180 min window. Severity was described according to both duration and nadir depth.

2.5 Development of the six study-specific features

Starting from the OGTT trajectories, we defined six study-specific summary features intended to capture complementary physiological dimensions of the coupled glucose–insulin response. These features were computed only in subjects with complete glucose and insulin profiles over the full 0–180 min OGTT. The six features were: glucose area under the curve (AUCG), log-transformed insulin area (ln AUCI), insulin recovery (RecI), late insulin fraction (TailFracI), insulin temporal centroid (\bar{t}), and relative centroid delay ($\Delta t_{\text{centroid}}$). Together, these features summarised total glucose exposure, total insulin exposure, persistence of late insulin elevation, the fraction of insulin exposure occurring in the late phase, the temporal centre of mass of the insulin response, and the relative delay of insulin with respect to glucose dynamics. Full formal

definitions are in the Supplementary Appendix.

2.6 Validation of the six study-specific features

The six study-specific features were evaluated within the study cohort to determine whether they captured physiologically meaningful metabolic heterogeneity beyond conventional glucose-based classification. Evaluation focused on four complementary aspects: phenotypic discrimination across glucose- and insulin-response categories; construct consistency relative to established fasting and dynamic OGTT-derived indices; structural consistency within the global multivariate organisation of the dataset; and discrimination capacity assessed through geometric and distance-based profiling.

2.7 Statistical and multivariate analysis

Continuous variables were summarised using measures of central tendency and dispersion appropriate to their distribution; categorical variables were reported as counts and percentages. The relationship between glucose-based and insulin-based classification was examined descriptively by cross-tabulation. Associations between conventional indices and the six study-specific features were analysed to quantify shared and complementary information. The higher-order structure of the dataset was investigated using principal component analysis, geometric profiling and distance-based analyses. All analyses were performed in MATLAB R2024a (MathWorks).

2.8 Quadrant assignment and continuous dysregulation score

Study-specific features were standardised against the reference population with normal glucose-response category by z-score transformation. Two normalised axes were defined: a glucose burden axis GL, derived from AUCG, and a late insulin persistence axis LIP, derived from RecI and TailFracI. Quadrants were assigned using fixed thresholds at 0 on both axes: Q1, $GL \leq 0$ and $LIP \leq 0$; Q2, $GL > 0$ and $LIP \leq 0$; Q3, $GL \leq 0$ and $LIP > 0$; Q4, $GL > 0$ and $LIP > 0$. The core dataset was restricted to profiles satisfying $GL \leq 10$ and $LIP \leq 20$.

A Mahalanobis-based OGTT dysregulation score was computed relative to Q1 in two feature spaces: a reduced 3D representation based on AUCG, \ln AUCI and \bar{I} , and a full 6D representation based on all six study-specific features. The 6D score was used as the principal continuous descriptor of OGTT dysregulation. Full formal definitions are reported in the Supplementary Appendix.

2.9 Ethical considerations

Retrospective observational study on anonymized clinical laboratory data from MEDyLAB srl. Performed in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki, EU GDPR, and guidelines of the Italian Data Protection Authority (Provvedimento n. 146, 5 giugno 2019). Formal IRB approval was not required: data derived from routine diagnostic tests, strictly anonymized, no clinical intervention. Analytical pipeline implemented

Figure 1 Classification algorithm of the hybrid OGTT glucose scheme (hOGTT). The algorithm applies three sequential decision steps to assign each OGTT glucose profile to one of four mutually exclusive categories. Step 1 screens for diabetes mellitus. Step 2 screens for impaired glucose tolerance. Step 3 distinguishes IFG from normal on fasting glucose. Reactive hypoglycaemia (any glucose ≤ 54 mg/dL) is flagged independently.

in MATLAB; AI-assisted support used exclusively for code review and language editing.

3 Results

3.1 Cohort characteristics

The study cohort included 273 individuals with complete glucose- and insulin-curve classification. Overall, 231 participants were female (84.6%) and 42 were male (15.4%). Median age was 42.0 years (IQR 30.8–53.0) and median BMI was 26.7 kg/m² (IQR 23.1–30.8). Baseline characteristics stratified by hOGTT glucose category are reported in Table 1.

Age increased progressively across categories, from a median of 37.0 years in hOGTT-Normal to 55.0 years in hOGTT-DM. Fasting glucose, 30-min glucose and 2-h glucose showed expected stepwise increases. Fasting insulin was highest in hOGTT-IFG [9.0 (5.8–9.0) mU/L], consistent with hepatic insulin resistance. HOMA-IR peaked in hOGTT-IFG [2.29 (1.49–3.03)]. The insulinogenic index (IGI) declined progressively from 1.21 (0.74–1.90) in hOGTT-Normal to 0.42 (0.28–0.85) in hOGTT-DM, indicating progressive beta-cell impairment.

3.2 Distribution of glucose- and insulin-response phenotypes

According to hOGTT, 163 subjects (59.7%) were classified as hOGTT-Normal, 29 (10.6%) as hOGTT-IFG, 52 (19.1%) as hOGTT-IGT, and 29 (10.6%) as hOGTT-DM. According to insulin-response classification, KC-I was the most frequent phenotype in 129 subjects (47.3%), followed by KC-III in 72 (26.4%), KC-IIA in 29 (10.6%), KC-V in 28 (10.3%), and KC-IIIB in 15 (5.5%). KC-IV was not observed in this cohort.

Table 1 Baseline characteristics of the study cohort stratified by hOGTT glucose-response category. Values: median (IQR).

Variable	hOGTT-Normal (n=163)	hOGTT-IFG (n=29)	hOGTT-IGT (n=52)	hOGTT-DM (n=29)
Age (years)	37.0 (27.2–46.0)	50.0 (41.8–61.0)	45.0 (35.5–54.5)	55.0 (47.5–66.2)
BMI (kg/m ²)	26.1 (23.1–30.1)	28.5 (24.2–30.7)	26.8 (23.0–32.7)	26.9 (21.7–36.2)
Fasting glucose (mg/dL)	89.0 (84.0–94.0)	104.0 (101.0–109.0)	96.5 (90.0–102.0)	111.0 (101.2–124.8)
30-min glucose (mg/dL)	128.0 (113.0–140.0)	159.0 (137.2–168.8)	164.0 (146.0–178.0)	202.0 (184.8–215.2)
2-h glucose (mg/dL)	86.0 (73.0–98.8)	98.0 (85.2–115.8)	115.0 (95.0–140.0)	134.0 (115.2–167.2)
Fasting insulin (mU/L)	5.7 (3.9–8.9)	9.0 (5.8–11.9)	7.4 (4.8–10.7)	5.4 (3.8–15.1)
30-min insulin (mU/L)	46.6 (27.5–72.0)	55.7 (44.7–76.8)	48.2 (27.5–72.8)	44.6 (30.2–74.6)
HOMA-IR	1.28 (0.83–1.96)	2.29 (1.49–3.03)	1.85 (1.13–2.68)	1.49 (1.09–4.09)
HOMA- β	88.2 (62.1–133.8)	74.0 (45.2–108.4)	83.4 (53.6–105.8)	50.1 (26.7–117.0)
IGI	1.21 (0.74–1.90)	0.94 (0.82–1.49)	0.55 (0.37–0.77)	0.42 (0.28–0.85)

3.3 Relationship between glucose-based and insulin-based classification

Cross-tabulation of glucose-response categories and insulin-response phenotypes showed that the two classification systems were related, but not interchangeable (Figure 2). Among subjects classified as normal by glucose criteria, KC-I was the most frequent insulin phenotype (89/163 cases; 54.6%). However, the remaining normal group was distributed across KC-IIA (10.4%), KC-IIB (3.7%), KC-III (16.0%), and KC-V (15.3%), indicating substantial insulin-response heterogeneity despite normoglycaemia.

In IGT, KC-III represented 46.2% of cases; in diabetes it rose to 58.6%, becoming the dominant insulin phenotype. The proportion of KC-I progressively declined from 54.6% in normal subjects to 20.7% in diabetes. Subjects within the same glucose-defined class often displayed markedly different insulin-response patterns, whereas progression toward dysglycaemia was accompanied by redistribution toward delayed and persistent insulin phenotypes.

3.4 Conventional OGTT-derived indices

ROC analyses based on conventional fasting and dynamic OGTT-derived indices showed that standard surrogate measures captured only part of the metabolic heterogeneity revealed by combined glucose-insulin phenotyping. Dynamic indices consistently outperformed fasting surrogates, but still represented only partial approximations of the integrated information contained in the complete OGTT response. Full descriptive summaries and ROC analyses are reported in the Supplementary Material (Tables S2–S3 and Figures S1–S6).

3.5 Reactive hypoglycaemia across glucose-response categories

Reactive hypoglycaemia (any OGTT glucose below 54 mg/dL) was observed in 54 of 226 subjects (23.9%). Among affected subjects, median nadir glucose was 49 mg/dL, median hypoglycaemic duration was 1 sampled time-point, and median glucose deficit was 5 mg/dL. Reactive hypoglycaemia was predominantly a late OGTT phenomenon: the first event occurred before 120 min in 5 subjects (9.3%), at 120 min in 6 (11.1%), and after 120 min in 43 (79.6%). Restricting

OGTT interpretation to the conventional 120 min end-point would have missed most hypoglycaemic events.

Reactive hypoglycaemia was distributed throughout the full spectrum of glycaemic phenotypes: observed in 36/150 subjects with normal glucose curves (24.0%), 5/23 IFG (21.7%), 9/40 IGT (22.5%), and 4/13 diabetes (30.8%). Regarding severity, events were mild in 20 subjects (37.0%), moderate in 27 (50.0%), and severe in 7 (13.0%). Most events were brief, involving a single sampled time-point in 41 of 54 affected subjects (75.9%).

3.6 Standardized OGTT feature space and quadrant allocation

Before defining the quadrant framework, the six standardized OGTT-derived features showed a coherent internal organization, with strong coupling among timing- and persistence-related variables and a stable low-dimensional structure (Supplementary Tables S10–S12).

The six study-specific features were standardized using the reference population with normal glucose-response category. Two physiologically interpretable axes were derived: a glucose burden axis $GL = Z_N(\text{AUCG})$ and a late insulin persistence axis $LIP = Z_N(\text{RecI}) + Z_N(\text{TailFracI})$. Quadrant allocation was performed using fixed thresholds at 0 on both axes. After application of the admissibility filter ($GL \leq 10$, $LIP \leq 20$), 226 OGTT profiles were retained. Their distribution was markedly non-uniform: 58 in Q1, 58 in Q2, 19 in Q3, and 91 in Q4 (Figure 4).

3.7 Q1 reference model and continuous dysregulation score

Q1 was taken as the physiological reference region. Mahalanobis distance was computed in both the reduced 3D (AUCG, \ln AUCI, \bar{t} I) and full 6D feature spaces. In the full 6D space, the upper physiological range corresponded to the 95th and 97.5th percentiles of 3.9173 and 4.0700. Median dysregulation scores increased progressively from Q1 to Q4, indicating that Mahalanobis distance preserved the directional hierarchy of the quadrant framework while expressing it on a continuous scale (Supplementary Figures S7–S9).

In ROC analysis, the 6D Mahalanobis score almost perfectly separated clinically normal Q1 from Q4 (AUC

Figure 2 Relationship between glucose-response categories and insulin-response phenotypes. A, Alluvial representation showing that subjects within the same glucose-defined class were distributed across multiple insulin-response patterns. B, Within-category proportional distribution of insulin-response phenotypes. Glucose-based classification and insulin-based phenotyping were related but not interchangeable.

Figure 3 Reactive hypoglycaemia during OGTT. A, Distribution of the OGTT time point at which the first hypoglycaemic event was observed. Most first events occurred after 120 min. B, Prevalence of reactive hypoglycaemia across glucose-response categories. Reactive hypoglycaemia was distributed across the full spectrum of glycaemic phenotypes.

0.996) and showed strong discrimination between Q2 and Q4 (AUC 0.935). The standardized OGTT feature space can be read at two complementary levels: a discrete level (GL and LIP allocate profiles to one of four quadrants) and a continuous level (Mahalanobis distance quantifies how far each profile lies from the physiological Q1 reference).

3.8 Clinical distribution of the dysregulation score

In the full 6D feature space, median values increased from 3.802 in the normal-glucose group to 5.280 in IFG, 7.147 in IGT, and 9.357 in diabetes, indicating a graded departure from the physiological Q1 reference. Using the 95th percentile of Q1 as threshold (3.9173), 72 of 150 normal-glucose subjects (48.0%) already lay outside the physiological range. The corresponding proportions were 13/23 in IFG (56.5%), 38/40 in IGT (95.0%), and 13/13 in diabetes (100.0%).

Figure 4 Standardized OGTT feature space and quadrant allocation. A, GL-LIP plane after feature standardization. Quadrants defined by fixed thresholds at 0 on GL (glucose burden) and LIP (late insulin persistence) axes. B, Distribution of core OGTT profiles across the four quadrants. The cohort partitioned into four metabolically distinct directional regions.

Internal heterogeneity within the normal-glucose subgroup was striking. Stratified by quadrant, the median 6D score was 2.196 in Q1, 3.360 in Q2, 6.770 in Q3, and 8.555 in Q4, showing that clinically similar glucose classifications could correspond to markedly different positions in the OGTT metabolic space (Figure 5).

4 Discussion

4.1 Glucose and insulin classification are related but not interchangeable

The present study shows that conventional OGTT interpretation based mainly on fasting and 120 min glucose thresholds captures only part of post-load metabolic heterogeneity. Glucose-response categories and insulin-response phenotypes were clearly related but not interchangeable: only 54.6% of subjects with

Figure 5 Clinical distribution of the 6D dysregulation score. Distribution across conventional glucose-response categories. The score increased progressively from Normal to Diabetes. Within the normal-glucose subgroup, substantial heterogeneity remained, with progressively higher scores from Q1 to Q4, supporting the concept of occult non-physiological OGTT profiles.

normal glucose curves showed the physiological KC-I insulin pattern, whereas KC-III became increasingly prevalent with worsening dysglycaemia, accounting for 46.2% of IGT and 58.6% of diabetes.

A central implication of these findings is that normal glucose tolerance did not necessarily correspond to physiological post-load regulation. In the full 6D feature space, the median Mahalanobis dysregulation score increased progressively from 3.802 in the normal-glucose group to 5.280 in IFG, 7.147 in IGT, and 9.357 in diabetes. More importantly, 72 of 150 normal-glucose subjects (48.0%) already lay above the 95th percentile of the physiological Q1 reference range in 6D. When the normal-glucose subgroup was stratified by quadrant, the median Mahalanobis score rose from 2.196 in Q1 to 3.360 in Q2, 6.770 in Q3, and 8.555 in Q4.

4.2 The six OGTT features reflect physiological structure

A second major finding is that the six OGTT-derived features did not behave as an arbitrary analytic construction. Their internal organisation was coherent and physiologically interpretable. This suggests that the dominant abnormality captured by the feature space was not simply the magnitude of glucose or insulin exposure, but the timing and persistence of the insulin response.

The quadrant framework provides a physiological reading of this structure. Because GL represents standardized glucose burden and LIP represents standardized late insulin persistence, the four quadrants describe distinct modes of coupling between the oral glucose load and the late phase of the insulin response. Q1 is closest to physiological post-load regulation; Q2 reflects high burden without marked late persistence; Q3 suggests relatively preserved glucose control at the cost of delayed or prolonged insulin output; and Q4 combines high burden with high late persistence and is the most disorganised profile. Within this framework, quadrants

indicate where a profile lies in the standardized OGTT space, whereas Mahalanobis distance indicates how far it lies from the physiological Q1 reference. The two readouts are complementary rather than competing representations.

4.3 A truncated OGTT at 120 min is often incomplete

A third major conclusion is that an OGTT truncated at 120 min is often incomplete. Reactive hypoglycaemia was present in 23.9% of the analysed core cohort, and 79.6% of first hypoglycaemic events occurred after 120 min. Even within the normal-glucose subgroup, reactive hypoglycaemia occurred in 24.0% of subjects. A 2h OGTT would therefore have missed most first hypoglycaemic events and discarded the late portion of the response from which several informative insulin-persistence features are derived.

These findings suggest that early dysmetabolism may involve altered temporal coupling between the oral glucose challenge and the insulin response, rather than a purely quantitative defect in insulin secretion. An altered enteroinsular signal is one plausible explanation, since the incretin effect normally amplifies insulin secretion after oral glucose and is reduced in type 2 diabetes, largely because the insulinotropic action of GIP is impaired while GLP-1 activity is relatively better preserved (20, 21). The present study did not include direct measurements of incretin hormones, glucagon, gastric emptying or insulin secretion kinetics, and therefore cannot establish mechanism. The defensible conclusion is narrower: one of the earliest detectable abnormalities in this dataset is a disturbance in the timing and resolution of the insulin response to an oral challenge, not merely an excess of glycaemia.

4.4 A layered reinterpretation of the OGTT

From a broader perspective, these findings support a layered reinterpretation of the OGTT. Conventional glucose categories remain clinically useful and diagnostically necessary, but they are too coarse to provide a sufficient description of post-load metabolic physiology. Insulin-response phenotypes expose hidden heterogeneity within those categories, the six-feature space shows that this heterogeneity is structured rather than random, and the Q1-based Mahalanobis score quantifies continuous deviation from the physiological reference.

4.5 Limitations and strengths

The analysis was retrospective, cross-sectional and derived from a single cohort. The population was strongly female-predominant. The proposed feature set, although physiologically interpretable, is study-specific rather than universally standardised, and the operational 6D threshold around MD = 4 should be treated as an internal physiological boundary rather than a diagnostic cutoff ready for immediate external adoption. These limitations temper generalisation, but they do not negate the internal consistency of the findings.

The main strengths are the prolonged 3h OGTT design, simultaneous glucose and insulin sampling, and

the integration of descriptive, geometric and distance-based analyses within a single physiological framework. Taken together, these findings support a broader interpretation of the OGTT as a metabolic phenotyping tool rather than a purely threshold-based diagnostic test.

5 Statements

Author contributions. Giuseppe Cardillo: conceptualization, methodology, software, formal analysis, investigation, data curation, visualization, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing, supervision.

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Conflict of interest. Giuseppe Cardillo is a 50% shareholder of MEDyLAB srl, from which the de-identified data were derived. The author declares this role did not influence study design, data analysis, interpretation of results, or decision to submit.

Data availability. The datasets generated and/or analysed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

AI disclosure. During the preparation of this manuscript, the author used Claude (Anthropic) to assist with language refinement and editorial revision. All scientific content, interpretations and final wording were critically reviewed by the author, who takes full responsibility for the integrity and accuracy of the manuscript.

Ethics statement. Retrospective study on de-identified clinical laboratory records. Under Italian regulations, formal Ethics Committee approval not required. Declaration of Helsinki; EU GDPR requirements for pseudonymized health data.

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Supplementary Appendix

Note on units. Throughout the feature computation, glucose is expressed in mmol/L (factor 0.0555) and insulin in pmol/L (factor 5.972), consistent with Methods 2.2. The reference center/scale and the Q1 parameters below are defined on this pmol/L scale; the magnitude-dependent insulin features ($\ln AUC_I$, Rec_I) must therefore be computed in pmol/L. The ratio and centroid features ($TailFrac_I$, \bar{t}_I , $\Delta t_{\text{centroid}}$) are unit-invariant.

S1. Step-by-step calculation of the six study-specific features

Consider an OGTT curve with

$$G = [86, 127, 146, 90, 88, 65, 49] \text{ mg/dL}, \quad I = [9.69, 55.30, 101.90, 93.40, 52.20, 17.40, 5.10] \text{ mU/L},$$

measured at $t = [0, 30, 60, 90, 120, 150, 180]$ min.

Insulin was converted to pmol/L (factor 5.972):

$$I = [57.8687, 330.2516, 608.5468, 557.7848, 311.7384, 103.9128, 30.4572] \text{ pmol/L}.$$

Glucose was converted to mmol/L (factor 0.0555):

$$G = [4.7730, 7.0485, 8.1030, 4.9950, 4.8840, 3.6075, 2.7195].$$

Using the trapezoidal weight vector $w_t = [30, 60, 60, 60, 60, 60, 30]$, the glucose area under the curve was

$$AUC_G = \frac{1}{2} w_t^T G = \frac{1}{2}(290.7 + 3318 + 6114 + 5604 + 3132 + 1044 + 153) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot 1943.055 = 971.5275.$$

The insulin area under the curve was computed analogously:

$$AUC_I = \frac{1}{2} w_t^T I = \frac{1}{2} \cdot 117383.84 = 58691.92.$$

The log-transformed insulin area was then

$$\ln AUC_I = \ln(1 + AUC_I) = \ln(58692.92) = 10.9801.$$

Insulin recovery was defined as

$$Rec_I = I_{180} - I_0 = 30.4572 - 57.8687 = -27.4115.$$

For the late insulin fraction, with $w_{\text{tail}} = [0, 0, 0, 0, 30, 60, 30]$:

$$TailFrac_I = \frac{w_{\text{tail}}^T I}{w_t^T I} = \frac{(30 \cdot 311.7384) + (60 \cdot 103.9128) + (30 \cdot 30.4572)}{117383.84} = \frac{16500.64}{117383.84} = 0.1406.$$

The temporal centroid of the insulin response was

$$\bar{t}_I = \frac{w_t^T (t \odot I)}{w_t^T I} = \frac{9,141,459.84}{117383.84} = 77.8766,$$

and the glucose temporal centroid analogously

$$\bar{t}_G = \frac{w_t^T (t \odot G)}{w_t^T G} = \frac{151148.70}{1943.055} = 77.7892.$$

Finally, the relative centroid delay was

$$\Delta t_{\text{centroid}} = \bar{t}_I - \bar{t}_G = 77.8766 - 77.7892 = 0.0874.$$

S2. Standardization of OGTT-derived features

For each feature f , normalization was performed by $ZN_f = (f - \text{center}_f)/\text{scale}_f$ using the normal-reference population ($N = 150$). In the canonical order $[AUC_G, \ln AUC_I, \bar{t}_I, Rec_I, TailFrac_I, \Delta t_{\text{centroid}}]$:

$$\text{center}_f = \begin{bmatrix} 938.22750 \\ 10.360072 \\ 76.429821 \\ -3.583200 \\ 0.184304 \\ -5.314119 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \text{scale}_f = \begin{bmatrix} 81.168750 \\ 0.403037 \\ 9.146845 \\ 20.304800 \\ 0.068427 \\ 8.321762 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Continuing the illustrative example (insulin in pmol/L), the six computed feature values and their standardized scores were:

$$\begin{aligned} ZN(\text{AUC}_G) &= (971.5275 - 938.22750)/81.168750 = 0.410256, \\ ZN(\ln \text{AUC}_I) &= (10.9801 - 10.360072)/0.403037 = 1.538326, \\ ZN(\bar{t}_I) &= (77.8766 - 76.429821)/9.146845 = 0.158178, \\ ZN(\text{Rec}_I) &= (-27.4115 - (-3.583200))/20.304800 = -1.173529, \\ ZN(\text{TailFrac}_I) &= (0.1406 - 0.184304)/0.068427 = -0.639135, \\ ZN(\Delta t_{\text{centroid}}) &= (0.0874 - (-5.314119))/8.321762 = 0.649089. \end{aligned}$$

Thus

$$x_{3D} = [0.410256, 1.538326, 0.158178]; \quad x_{6D} = [0.410256, 1.538326, 0.158178, -1.173529, -0.639135, 0.649089].$$

S3. Quadrant assignment

The two axes used for quadrant assignment were $GL = ZN(\text{AUC}_G)$ and $LIP = ZN(\text{Rec}_I) + ZN(\text{TailFrac}_I)$. Quadrants: Q1 ($GL \leq 0, LIP \leq 0$), Q2 ($GL > 0, LIP \leq 0$), Q3 ($GL \leq 0, LIP > 0$), Q4 ($GL > 0, LIP > 0$).

For the example:

$$GL = ZN(\text{AUC}_G) = 0.410256, \quad LIP = ZN(\text{Rec}_I) + ZN(\text{TailFrac}_I) = -1.173529 + (-0.639135) = -1.812664.$$

Since $GL > 0$ and $LIP \leq 0$, this profile was assigned to **Q2**.

S4. Q1 reference parameters for the Mahalanobis score

The reduced 3D reference parameters were $\mu_{3D} = [-1.014049, -0.445435, -0.932762]$ with

$$\Sigma_{3D} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.179987 & 0.078216 & 0.022888 \\ 0.078216 & 0.749493 & -0.016139 \\ 0.022888 & -0.016139 & 0.350498 \end{bmatrix}.$$

The full 6D reference parameters were $\mu_{6D} = [-1.014049, -0.445435, -0.932762, -0.547547, -0.862284, -0.957731]$ with

$$\Sigma_{6D} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.179987 & 0.078216 & 0.022888 & -0.019509 & 0.011944 & 0.013114 \\ 0.078216 & 0.749493 & -0.016139 & -0.052229 & -0.030867 & 0.022443 \\ 0.022888 & -0.016139 & 0.350498 & -0.016606 & 0.203807 & 0.394850 \\ -0.019509 & -0.052229 & -0.016606 & 0.040657 & -0.015218 & -0.002901 \\ 0.011944 & -0.030867 & 0.203807 & -0.015218 & 0.198555 & 0.175868 \\ 0.013114 & 0.022443 & 0.394850 & -0.002901 & 0.175868 & 0.591906 \end{bmatrix}.$$

The Mahalanobis score was computed as $MD = \sqrt{(x - \mu_{Q1})^T \Sigma_{Q1}^{-1} (x - \mu_{Q1})}$. For the example:

$$MD_{6D} = \sqrt{23.0252} = 4.7985, \quad MD_{3D} = \sqrt{16.5308} = 4.0658.$$

Both values exceeded the 6D physiological 95th percentile (3.9173) and the 97.5th percentile (4.0700), indicating that the OGTT profile lay outside the physiological Q1 reference space. The reduced 3D score confirmed the same qualitative conclusion. In practical terms, this worked example shows that an OGTT curve may be assigned to a specific metabolic quadrant (here Q2) and, at the same time, quantified on a continuous physiological-to-dysregulated scale using the Mahalanobis distance from Q1.

Erratum note (this revision). In the originally published appendix the worked example displayed insulin in mU/L while the reference center/scale were defined on the pmol/L scale, producing inconsistent $ZN(\ln \text{AUC}_I)$, $ZN(\text{Rec}_I)$, LIP and MD values for the example only. The values above are recomputed with insulin in pmol/L. The quadrant assignment (Q2) and the qualitative conclusion (profile beyond the P95 reference) are unchanged. All published cohort-level results, reference constants and percentiles are unaffected.

Supplementary Table S1. Cross-tabulation of insulin-response phenotypes across glucose-response categories

Glucose Curves	Insulin Curves					Total
	KC-I	KC-IIA	KC-IIB	KC-III	KC-V	
Normal	89 (54.6%)	17 (10.4%)	6 (3.7%)	26 (16.0%)	25 (15.3%)	163
IFG	18 (62.1%)	4 (13.8%)	2 (6.9%)	5 (17.2%)	0 (0.0%)	29
IGT	16 (30.8%)	5 (9.6%)	5 (9.6%)	24 (46.2%)	2 (3.8%)	52
Diabetes	6 (20.7%)	3 (10.3%)	2 (6.9%)	17 (58.6%)	1 (3.4%)	29
Total	129	29	15	72	28	273

Supplementary Table S2. Descriptive characteristics of fasting-derived indices in the overall cohort

Index	Median (IQR)	N
Belfiore	1.2500 (1.0575-1.4600)	273
Bennett	0.6300 (0.5200-0.8425)	273
FIRI	1.3356 (0.8304-2.0022)	273
HOMA-B	83.5200 (52.2800-123.7200)	273
HOMA-IR	1.4900 (0.9200-2.2225)	273
IGR	1.2400 (0.8100-1.8625)	273
IS	10.2200 (6.6900-15.3225)	273
McAuley	9.5400 (7.6775-11.0900)	107
QUICKI	0.3598 (0.3383-0.3886)	273
Raynaud	6.2000 (4.1700-9.9100)	273
SPINA-DI	4.2612 (3.7544-4.9638)	273
SPINA-GB	1.5300 (0.9975-2.2750)	273
SPINA-GR	2.7000 (1.7975-4.5075)	273
TyG	4.4100 (4.1925-4.6250)	107

Supplementary Figure S1. ROC analysis of fasting-derived indices for glucose-defined normal vs not-normal curves.

Glycemic curves - Normal vs Not Normal

Supplementary Figure S2. ROC analysis of fasting-derived indices for insulin-defined normal vs not-normal curves.

Insulinemic curves - Normal vs Not Normal

Supplementary Figure S3. ROC analysis of fasting-derived indices for OGTT-defined normal vs not-normal subjects.

OGTT curves - Normal vs Not Normal

Supplementary Table S3. Summary of dynamic OGTT-derived indices in the overall cohort

Index	Median (IQR)	N
Belfiore	1.0400 (0.8400-1.2925)	273
Cederholm	91.9150 (71.1900-125.8200)	262
DI	4.6720 (2.7074-9.2559)	273
Gutt	93.2050 (73.3700-122.1000)	262
ISI	0.8700 (0.5150-1.4450)	273
Kanauchi	7.5700 (6.7200-8.1825)	273
Matsuda	5.7500 (3.9275-8.8900)	273
OGIS	465.2400 (413.8800-508.1400)	262
PREDIM	6.0300 (4.6000-7.9500)	262
SIisOGTT	0.2800 (0.2700-0.3000)	273
Stumvoll	0.0994 (0.0786-0.1140)	273

Supplementary Figure S4. ROC analysis of dynamic OGTT-derived indices for glucose-defined normal vs not-normal curves.

Glycemic curves - Normal vs Not Normal

Supplementary Figure S5. ROC analysis of dynamic OGTT-derived indices for insulin-defined normal vs not-normal curves.

Insulinemic curves - Normal vs Not Normal

Supplementary Figure S6. ROC analysis of dynamic OGTT-derived indices for OGTT-defined normal vs not-normal subjects

OGTT curves - Normal vs Not Normal

Supplementary Table S4. Exact timing of first reactive hypoglycaemic event and duration/depth classes in the overall cohort. Reactive hypoglycaemia was defined as any OGTT glucose value <54 mg/dL. Mild hypoglycaemia was defined if 50 mg/dL < G < 54 mg/dL; moderate 40 mg/dL < G ≤ 50 mg/dL; severe G ≤ 40 mg/dL.

Variable	Value
Subjects analysed, n	226
Reactive hypoglycaemia, n (%)	54 (23.9)
Median nadir glucose among affected curves, mg/dL	49
Median hypoglycaemic duration among affected curves, sampled time-points	1
Median glucose deficit below threshold among affected curves, mg/dL	5
First event at 60 min, n/N hypo (%)	2/54 (3.7)
First event at 90 min, n/N hypo (%)	3/54 (5.6)
First event at 120 min, n/N hypo (%)	6/54 (11.1)
First event at 150 min, n/N hypo (%)	19/54 (35.2)
First event at 180 min, n/N hypo (%)	24/54 (44.4)
Mild reactive hypoglycaemia, n/N total (%)	20/226 (8.8)
Moderate reactive hypoglycaemia, n/N total (%)	27/226 (11.9)
Severe reactive hypoglycaemia, n/N total (%)	7/226 (3.1)
Mild reactive hypoglycaemia, n/N hypo (%)	20/54 (37.0)
Moderate reactive hypoglycaemia, n/N hypo (%)	27/54 (50.0)
Severe reactive hypoglycaemia, n/N hypo (%)	7/54 (13.0)
One-point event, n/N total (%)	41/226 (18.1)
Two-point event, n/N total (%)	10/226 (4.4)
≥3-point event, n/N total (%)	3/226 (1.3)

Supplementary Table S5. Reactive hypoglycaemia across insulin-response phenotypes.

Insulin-response phenotype	N	Reactive hypoglycaemia, n (%)
KC-I	128	33 (25.8)
KC-IIA	28	7 (25.0)
KC-IIB	10	4 (40.0)
KC-III	39	8 (20.5)
KC-V	21	2 (9.5)

Supplementary Table S6. Reactive hypoglycaemia across combined glucose-response categories and insulin-response phenotypes.

Glucose-response category	Insulin-response phenotype	N	Reactive hypoglycaemia, n (%)
NGT	KC-I	89	25 (28.1)
NGT	KC-IIA	17	5 (29.4)
NGT	KC-IIB	5	2 (40.0)
NGT	KC-III	21	2 (9.5)
NGT	KC-V	18	2 (11.1)
IFG	KC-I	17	2 (11.8)
IFG	KC-IIA	4	1 (25.0)
IFG	KC-IIB	1	1 (100.0)
IFG	KC-III	1	1 (100.0)
IGT	KC-I	16	4 (25.0)
IGT	KC-IIA	5	0 (0.0)
IGT	KC-IIB	4	1 (25.0)
IGT	KC-III	13	4 (30.8)
IGT	KC-V	2	0 (0.0)
Diabetes	KC-I	6	2 (33.3)
Diabetes	KC-IIA	2	1 (50.0)
Diabetes	KC-III	4	1 (25.0)
Diabetes	KC-V	1	0 (0.0)

Supplementary Table S7. Reactive hypoglycaemia across insulin-response phenotypes within the normal-glucose subgroup.

Variable		Value
Subjects with normal glucose curves, n		150
Reactive hypoglycaemia, n (%)		36 (24.0)
First event before 120 min, n/N hypo (%)		5/36 (13.9)
First event at 120 min, n/N hypo (%)		4/36 (11.1)
First event after 120 min, n/N hypo (%)		27/36 (75.0)
Median nadir glucose among affected curves, mg/dL		48.5
Median hypoglycaemic duration among affected curves, sampled time-points		1
Median glucose deficit below threshold among affected curves, mg/dL		5.5
Insulin-response phenotype	N	Reactive hypoglycaemia, n (%)
KC-I	89	25 (28.1)
KC-IIA	17	5 (29.4)
KC-IIB	5	2 (40.0)
KC-III	21	2 (9.5)
KC-V	18	2 (11.1)

Supplementary Table S8. Comparison of subjects with and without reactive hypoglycaemia in the overall cohort.

Variable	N without hypo	N with hypo	Median without hypo	Median with hypo	p value	R
Hypo duration	172	54	0	1	3.5403e-50	
Hypo duration late	172	54	0	1	6.3958e-48	
Hypo deficit	172	54	0	5	3.3298e-44	
Hypo deficit late	172	54	0	4	4.3552e-42	
Hypo nadir	172	54	70.5	49	1.5519e-28	
Hypo nadir late	172	54	71	50	4.8030e-27	
TailFrac ₁	172	54	0.21226	0.13681	0.0003377	
AUC _G	172	54	1021.1	940.72	0.0016986	
ScoreMD Q1 6D	172	54	5.2459	3.7036	0.0024956	
\bar{t}_1	172	54	79.313	73.614	0.0077300	
Rec ₁	172	54	2.0603	-5.6734	0.0097724	
ln(AUC ₁)	172	54	10.446	10.519	0.50948	
$\Delta t_{\text{centroid}}$	172	54	-3.2853	-2.2224	0.87395	

Supplementary Table S9. Comparison of subjects with and without reactive hypoglycaemia within the normal-glucose subgroup

Variable	N without hypo	N with hypo	Median without hypo	Median with hypo	p value	Rank-biserial effect size
Hypo duration	114	36	0	1	1.0058e-33	-1.00000
Hypo duration late	114	36	0	1	1.7089e-31	-0.94444
Hypo deficit	114	36	0	5.5	2.8884e-31	-0.94444
Hypo deficit late	114	36	0	4	3.9584e-29	-0.88889
Hypo nadir	114	36	68	48.5	1.6928e-19	1.00000
Hypo nadir late	114	36	69.5	50	6.8481e-18	0.95419
AUC _G	114	36	953.21	836.66	8.2826e-06	0.49391
TailFrac _I	114	36	0.20853	0.13576	0.00027585	0.40302
ScoreMD Q1 6D	114	36	4.2527	2.9090	0.0035036	0.32359
\bar{t}_I	114	36	77.810	70.906	0.0068493	0.29971
Rec _I	114	36	-1.1645	-7.1664	0.040514	0.22710
$\Delta t_{\text{centroid}}$	114	36	-5.2100	-6.6121	0.53640	0.06871
ln(AUC _I)	114	36	10.358	10.486	0.58530	-0.06067

Supplementary Table S10. Most relevant pairwise Spearman correlations among the six study-specific features in the core dataset.

Pair of features	Spearman rho	p value	Interpretation
$\Delta t_{\text{centroid}}$ vs \bar{t}_I	0.925	<0.0001	Very strong concordance between relative delay and absolute timing of insulin response
TailFrac _I vs \bar{t}_I	0.924	<0.0001	Late insulin fraction closely tracks delayed insulin timing
TailFrac _I vs $\Delta t_{\text{centroid}}$	0.772	<0.0001	Greater late insulin burden is associated with delayed insulin response relative to glucose
Rec _I vs \bar{t}_I	0.674	<0.0001	Persistent insulin elevation at 180 min is linked to later insulin timing
Rec _I vs TailFrac _I	0.659	<0.0001	Late persistence and late-phase fraction capture related but not identical processes
Rec _I vs $\Delta t_{\text{centroid}}$	0.603	<0.0001	Greater residual insulin is associated with delayed insulin response
AUC _G vs $\Delta t_{\text{centroid}}$	0.497	<0.0001	Higher glucose burden is associated with delayed insulin dynamics
AUC _G vs \bar{t}_I	0.472	<0.0001	Higher glucose exposure is associated with later insulin timing
AUC _G vs TailFrac _I	0.382	<0.0001	Higher glucose burden is associated with more late-phase insulin exposure
AUC _G vs ln(AUC _I)	0.380	<0.0001	Glucose and insulin burden are related, but not redundant
AUC _G vs Rec _I	0.305	<0.0001	Greater glucose exposure is modestly associated with residual insulin at 180 min
ln(AUC _I) vs $\Delta t_{\text{centroid}}$	0.319	<0.0001	Total insulin exposure is only moderately related to delayed response

Supplementary Table S11. Principal component analysis of the six study-specific features: explained variance and dominant loadings.

Principal component	Explained variance (%)	Cumulative variance (%)	Dominant positive loadings	Physiological interpretation
PC1	60.57	60.57	\bar{t}_I (0.502), $\Delta t_{\text{centroid}}$ (0.476), TailFrac _I (0.466), Rec _I (0.379)	Timing and persistence of the insulin response
PC2	16.64	77.21	logAUC _I (0.787), AUC _G (0.464)	Overall response magnitude / metabolic burden
PC3	11.22	88.43	AUC _G (0.635), $\Delta t_{\text{centroid}}$ (0.157), \bar{t}_I (0.087)	Residual variance not captured by the first two components

Supplementary Table S12. Bootstrap stability of explained variance for the principal components derived from the six study-specific features.

Principal component	Bootstrap mean explained variance (%)	SD
PC1	60.63	1.03
PC2	16.66	0.74
PC3	11.28	0.69
PC4	7.78	0.37
PC5	3.32	0.17
PC6	0.34	0.02

Supplementary Figure S7. Three-dimensional rendering of the reduced standardized OGTT feature space. Subjects are shown in the reduced 3D representation defined by standardized AUC_G , $\ln(AUC_I)$, and t_I , and are colored according to quadrant assignment. The semi-transparent teal ellipsoid represents the empirical Q1 reference region in 3D space. The figure provides a geometric visualization of the relationship between discrete quadrant allocation and continuous spatial displacement from the physiological Q1 reference domain.

Supplementary Table S13. Centroid coordinates of the four predefined metabolic quadrants in 3D and 6D feature space.

Space	Quadrant	N	AUC _G	logAUC _I	\bar{t}_I	Rec _I	TailFrac _I
3D	Q2	58	0.277	0.097	-0.565		
3D	Q4	91	0.642	0.260	0.863		
3D	Q1	58	-1.012	-0.432	-0.953		
3D	Q3	19	-0.918	-0.260	0.406		
6D	Q2	58	0.277	0.097	-0.565	-0.650	-0.703
6D	Q4	91	0.642	0.260	0.863	0.658	0.874
6D	Q1	58	-1.012	-0.432	-0.953	-0.556	-0.882
6D	Q3	19	-0.918	-0.260	0.406	0.463	0.557

Supplementary Table S14. Pairwise centroid distances among the four predefined metabolic quadrants in 3D and 6D feature space.

Space	Comparison	Euclidean centroid distance	Mahalanobis centroid distance
3D	Q2 vs Q4	1.482	2.326
3D	Q2 vs Q1	1.447	2.616
3D	Q2 vs Q3	1.581	3.068
3D	Q4 vs Q1	2.552	3.388
3D	Q4 vs Q3	1.706	2.243
3D	Q1 vs Q3	1.373	2.542
6D	Q2 vs Q4	2.736	2.800
6D	Q2 vs Q1	1.608	2.719
6D	Q2 vs Q3	2.405	3.630
6D	Q4 vs Q1	3.744	3.677
6D	Q4 vs Q3	1.785	2.273
6D	Q1 vs Q3	2.611	3.555

Supplementary Table S15. Separation scores among the four predefined metabolic quadrants in 3D and 6D feature space.

Space	Comparison	Pooled within-group spread	Euclidean centroid distance	Mahalanobis centroid distance	Separation (Euclidean)	Separation (Mahalanobis)
3D	Q2 vs Q4	1.574	1.482	2.326	0.942	1.478
3D	Q2 vs Q1	1.573	1.447	2.616	0.920	1.662
3D	Q2 vs Q3	1.566	1.581	3.068	1.009	1.959
3D	Q4 vs Q1	1.599	2.552	3.388	1.596	2.119
3D	Q4 vs Q3	1.592	1.706	2.243	1.072	1.409
3D	Q1 vs Q3	1.591	1.373	2.542	0.863	1.598
6D	Q2 vs Q4	2.313	2.736	2.800	1.183	1.210
6D	Q2 vs Q1	2.314	1.608	2.719	0.695	1.175
6D	Q2 vs Q3	2.305	2.405	3.630	1.044	1.575
6D	Q4 vs Q1	2.338	3.744	3.677	1.601	1.573
6D	Q4 vs Q3	2.329	1.785	2.273	0.766	0.976
6D	Q1 vs Q3	2.329	2.611	3.555	1.121	1.526

Supplementary Table S16. Subject reassignment performance for the four predefined metabolic quadrants in 3D and 6D feature space.

Space	True quadrant	N	Correct assignments	Correct assignment rate (%)
3D	Q2	58	51	87.93
3D	Q4	91	82	90.11
3D	Q1	58	49	84.48
3D	Q3	19	16	84.21
6D	Q2	58	50	86.21
6D	Q4	91	90	98.90
6D	Q1	58	53	91.38
6D	Q3	19	17	89.47

Supplementary Figure S8. 6D OGTT dysregulation score across quadrants.

Violin plots and jittered observations show the distribution of the 6D Mahalanobis dysregulation score in Q1-Q4. Red points indicate group medians. The horizontal dashed line marks the operational Q1 cutoff at MD = 4. The score increased progressively from Q1 to Q4, indicating that Mahalanobis distance provided a continuous measure of deviation from the physiological Q1 reference while preserving the directional hierarchy defined by quadrant allocation.

Supplementary Figure S9. ROC analysis of the 3D and 6D Mahalanobis dysregulation scores for selected quadrant comparisons. Panel A shows discrimination between clinically normal subjects in Q1 and Q4. Both scores performed very strongly, with AUC values of 0.976 for the 3D score and 0.996 for the 6D score. Panel B shows discrimination between Q2 and Q4. In this comparison, the 6D score outperformed the 3D score (AUC 0.935 vs 0.748), indicating that the full six-feature representation provided substantially better separation in intermediate-to-advanced metabolic dysregulation. The dashed diagonal line represents chance-level discrimination.

Supplementary Table S17. Reactive hypoglycaemia across metabolic quadrants in the overall cohort and in the normal-glucose subgroup.

Cohort	Quadrant	N	Reactive hypoglycaemia, n (%)
Overall cohort	Q1	58	23 (39.7)
Overall cohort	Q2	58	16 (27.6)
Overall cohort	Q3	19	4 (21.1)
Overall cohort	Q4	91	11 (12.1)
Normal glucose curves only	Q1	56	23 (41.1)
Normal glucose curves only	Q2	26	5 (19.2)
Normal glucose curves only	Q3	19	4 (21.1)
Normal glucose curves only	Q4	49	4 (8.2)